

DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF HYBRID DAIRY PACKING MACHINE USING PLC

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Abstract-Automation refers to a wide range of technologies and reducing human involvement in the processes. Nowadays, automation existing in packing various dairy products. But still there are some rural areas where packing of dairy products was done manually. The existing machine is expensive and it pack only one kind of dairy product and out of reach for small scale enterprises. It is necessary to build a lowcost packing machine using existing techniques which should consume less time and easy way to pack the various dairy products in a single packing machine. This project has a seperate row of tanks which contains various dairy products, we used three tanks for milk, curd and buttermilk even if we want to add another liquid dairy product it can add alongside with tanks and it has one boiler and a packing tank with a DC motor connected with a wing. The boiler and the packing tank connected by a one inch PVC[Polyvinyl Chloride] -pipe in a straight line the dairy tanks will be connected perpendicular to the one inch pipe by a half inch PVC-pipe. Each tank has a float switch to monitor the tank whether it is occupied or empty. And in between the pipe and each tank there is a solenoid valve that controls the flow of liquids. There are switches to select the dairy product to be packed. After it starts to pack the dairy product and after it ends then the valve of boiler will open and the motor starts to run and the hot water get scattered and cleans the packing tank. The entire operation is controlled by PLC. This product saves the time and reduces cost of packing.

Keywords - PLC,DC Motor,Float Switch.

I. INTRODUCTION

Packing of dairy products is done automatically in numerous packing industries but it costs too high for small scale enterprises. So the packing was done manually in those places. The small enterprises only pack a numerous number of pack and at small quantity. Efficient packing of these products is crucial not only to preserve the freshness and quality of the products but also to ensure their safe transportation and storage. To meet market demands and minimize spoilage, dairy packing processes need to be fast and efficient. Delays in packing can lead to significant losses due to the short shelf life of the products. Even though it happens manually it is not a hygienic process and consumes a lot of time and a large man power.

The existing system for pack dairy product only pack a single product and it prize is high and at high maintenance costs. Some systems may not be easily adaptable to different sizes or types of packaging, limiting their utility for various products. The packing of dairy product packing multiple dairy products in a single machine offers several advantages that motivate companies to invest in such versatile packaging solutions. Investing in a single machine that can handle various products can significantly reduce the need for multiple specialized machines, thereby saving on capital expenditure.

In this paper we propose a methodology that can lead to significant reductions in energy usage, which is both cost-effective and better for the environment. Implementing a multi-product packing machine can be a strategic decision that aligns with broader

operational goals, such as increasing efficiency, reducing costs, and improving environmental sustainability.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1METHODOLOGY

The packing machine contains three tanks. One boiler, one packing tank cube like structures. When we put the dairy product inside it, the float switch starts sensing. When it is starts sense, then it get signal from each of the float switches which was connected to the bottom of the each and every tanks. After getting signals from all float switches then it starts to get packed with the preference which was already been programmed or else we can give also any desired product by a switch. If it get signal from the float switch of the particular tank then it starts to pack the desired product as preferred.

Afterwards that closes the valve of the tank which has been used and the valve of the boiler will opens, it starts to flow into the packing tank. The motor starts to rotate which has been powered by the SIEMENS PLC and it splashes the hot water in the packing tank and it starts to clean. After the process the required dairy product has been packed. If there is no signal from first float switch, the PLC checks the next float switch in second tank, if it is high, the packing process begins. The process continue to third tank if second float switch becomes false.

The same DC source through SMPS/RPS given to the SIEMENS PLC, float switch as input. SIEMENS PLC controls the input of dairy product to the packing tank using solenoid valve for the confined

amount of dairy. After loading of dairy into the tank, the position is controlled by float switches by providing feedback to the float switches. The flow chart is shown in Fig 1.

Fig 1: Flow chart

2.2 CAD MODELLING

The development of a Solid Works model is a crucial phase of the manufacturing endeavour. The component parts are assembled. Once the part drawings are created according to the dimensions supplied at the beginning of the project. The packing machine we provide which consists of main CAD parts such as tanks, valves, DC motor, and the metal frame and base. Using basic geometric shapes to create frame. The CAD designs of the parts would be displayed in fig 2

Fig 2: 3D model of Hybrid Dairy packing machine

2.3 MATERIALS USED

S.No	COMPONENTSNAME	QUANTITY
1.	Cylindrical Vessel	5
2.	Solenoid Valve	5
3.	Float switch	5
4.	12VDC motor	1
5.	PLC	1
6.	PVC pipe	10mtrs
7.	Pipe fittings	8
8.	Steel metal frame	6mtrs

2.3.1 Mass of the components

Material used	=	Steel
Weight of the Frame	=	6 kg
Weight of the Cylinder	=	1.5kg
Weight of others	=	2 kg
Total weight of the system	=	9.5 kg

2.4 FABRICATED MODEL

The fabricated model of a Hybrid dairy packing machine provides a feasible representation of the design concept, allowing it as hands-on evaluation and validation of its functionality, performance, and suitability for intended applications as shown in Fig.3.

Figure.3: Fabricated Model

III. CONCLUSION

This project is mainly focused on the packing of liquid dairy products like milk, curd, buttermilk. There is no machine exist in the market for packing these dairy products in a single machine with a compact size and affordable prize. The existing machines are cost around 50,000 and above. For each dairy product mentioned above buy a new machine with a same cost and it is not suitable for the small-scale industries and as a commercial product. So, this machine is mainly focused to pack all these dairy products in a single machine with a simple process, with an affordable prize and it can consumed by all the consumers and it also used as a household product. This product does not require a huge space. It will be placed in a confined space. It does not require any skilled labour to control the machine. It can be operated by an ordinary people. It reduces the manual work in packing the dairy. Within a short time, it can pack the huge number of small quantity dairy compare with the manual work of packing dairy. This will also help in time consuming and quick cleaning processes.

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